

XML Format for CRC-Cohort data import into CCDC

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1 Introduction

This document provides documentation on how to construct the XML file to import the data for the CRC-Cohort contributors into the CCDC service. It is generated based on the XSD definition, which defines constraints on the XML to be imported into the CCDC.

Please note that using XML it is possible to import incomplete data, to allow for semi-automated import process:

1. the data, which biobanks have already structured, are imported via XML import,
2. each individual patient case is manually completed using CCDC.

For this reason, the XML import does not require all the data elements marked as REQUIRED in the data model. In the manual editing using CCDC web interface, before each patient can be saved, completeness of all the REQUIRED fields is checked.

2 Patient Pseudonyms

Pseudonyms of patients must be generated in compliance with the Data Protection Policy of CRC-Cohort. They are written into `<Identifier>...</Identifier>` element of the XML, as demonstrated in the example XML.

3 Forms

3.1 form_28_ver-27 - Form

Required data elements

- Dataelement_14_3 - MM_MICROSAT_INSTABILITY
- Dataelement_15_2 - MM_MISMATCH_REPAIR_GE
- Dataelement_20_3 - MM_KRAS_MUTATION_KRAS_EX2
- Dataelement_21_5 - MM_KRAS_MUTATION_KRAS_EX3
- Dataelement_22_4 - MM_KRAS_MUTATION_KRAS_EX4
- Dataelement_23_5 - MM_KRAS_MUTATION_NRAS_EX2
- Dataelement_24_4 - MM_KRAS_MUTATION_NRAS_EX3
- Dataelement_25_3 - MM_KRAS_MUTATION_NRAS_EX4
- Dataelement_30_3 - DIAG_MRI_DONE
- Dataelement_31_3 - DIAG_CT_DONE
- Dataelement_3_1 - AGE_AT_PRIMARY_DIAGNOSIS
- Dataelement_5_2 - VITAL_STATUS
- Dataelement_61_5 - DIAG_LIVER_IMAGING_DONE
- Dataelement_63_4 - DIAG_X_DONE
- Dataelement_7_2 - OVERALL_SURVIVAL_STATUS
- Dataelement_85_1 - SEX
- Dataelement_88_1 - DIAG_COLONOSCOPY

Optional data elements

- Dataelement_16_3 - MM_RISK_SITUATION_HNPCC
- Dataelement_2_2 - CLINICAL_STUDY_PARTICIPANT
- Dataelement_4_3 - TIME_OF_RECURRENCE_RELATIVE
- Dataelement_51_3 - DATE_DIAGNOSIS
- Dataelement_87_1 - BRAF_PIC3CA_HER_MUTATION_STATUS

Other data elements

- Dataelement_6_3 - VITAL_STATUS_TIMESTAMP
Level: if(VITAL_STATUS!=UNKNOWN){REQUIRED}else{OPTIONAL}

3.2 form_29_ver-5 - Form5

Required data elements

- Dataelement_12_4 - RADIATION_THERAPY_START_RELATIVE
- Dataelement_13_2 - RADIATION_THERAPY_END_RELATIVE

Optional data elements None.

Other data elements None.

3.3 form_30_ver-3 - Form6

Required data elements

- Dataelement_35_3 - TARGETED_THERAPY_START_RELATIVE

Optional data elements

- Dataelement_36_1 - TARGETED_THERAPY_END_RELATIVE

Other data elements None.

3.4 form_31_ver-2 - Form4

Required data elements

- Dataelement_33_1 - THERAPY_RESPONSE
- Dataelement_34_1 - THERAPY_RESPONSE_TIMESTAMP_RELATIVE

Optional data elements None.

Other data elements None.

3.5 form_32_ver-8 - Form

Required data elements

- Dataelement_49_1 - SURGERY_TYPE
- Dataelement_8_3 - SURGERY_START_RELATIVE
- Dataelement_93_1 - SURGERY_LOCATION
- Dataelement_9_2 - SURGERY_RADICALITY

Optional data elements

- Dataelement_67_1 - SURGERY_TYPE_OTHER

Other data elements None.

3.6 form_33_ver-10 - Form3

Required data elements

- Dataelement_10_2 - PHARMACOTHERAPY_START_RELATIVE
- Dataelement_11_2 - PHARMACOTHERAPY_END_RELATIVE
- Dataelement_59_5 - PHARMACOTHERAPY_SCHEME

Optional data elements None.

Other data elements

- Dataelement_81_3 - PHARMACOTHERAPY_SCHEME_DESCRIPTION
Level: if(PHARMACOTHERAPY_SCHEME==Other){REQUIRED}else{OPTIONAL}

3.7 form_34_ver-22 - Form2

Required data elements

- Dataelement_53_3 - WHO_GRADE_VERSION
- Dataelement_68_2 - HIST_METASTASIS
- Dataelement_70_2 - UICC_STAGE
- Dataelement_71_1 - TNM_PRIMARY_TUMOR
- Dataelement_73_3 - UICC_VERSION

- Dataelement_75_1 - TNM_DISTANT_METASTASIS
- Dataelement_77_1 - TNM_REGIONAL_LYMPH_NODES
- Dataelement_83_1 - WHO_GRADE
- Dataelement_91_1 - HIST_MORPHOLOGY
- Dataelement_92_1 - HIST_LOCALIZATION

Optional data elements

- Dataelement_57_3 - DIGITAL_IMAGING_AVAILABILITY
- Dataelement_58_2 - DIGITAL_IMAGING_INVASION_FRONT_AVAILABILITY
- Dataelement_82_1 - BIOLOGICAL_MATERIAL_FROM_RECURRENCE_AVAILABLE

Other data elements None.

3.8 form_35_ver-6 - Form1

Required data elements

- Dataelement_54_2 - SAMPLE_MATERIAL_TYPE
- Dataelement_55_2 - SAMPLE_PRESERVATION_MODE
- Dataelement_56_2 - SAMPLE_ID
- Dataelement_89_3 - YEAR_OF_SAMPLE_COLLECTION

Optional data elements None.

Other data elements None.

4 Data Elements

This section provides documentation of individual data elements, based on CRC-Cohort data model and XSD.

4.1 Dataelement_10_2 - PHARMACOTHERAPY_START_RELATIVE

XSD label Dataelement_10_2

Data model label PHARMACOTHERAPY_START_RELATIVE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Date of start of pharamacotherapy

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

NATURAL_NUMBER [week] ($0 \leq x$)

XSD parent form Form3 - form_33_ver-10

XSD description

Start of the drug intake in weeks since initial diagnosis.

Data model description

Start of the drug intake in weeks since initial diagnosis.

4.2 Dataelement_11_2 - PHARMACOTHERAPY_END_RELATIVE

XSD label Dataelement_11_2

Data model label PHARMACOTHERAPY_END_RELATIVE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Date of end of pharamcotherapy

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

NATURAL_NUMBER [week] ($0 \leq x$)

XSD parent form Form3 - form_33_ver-10

XSD description

End of the drug intake in weeks since initial diagnosis.

Data model description

End of the drug intake in weeks since initial diagnosis.

4.3 Dataelement_12_4 - RADIATION_THERAPY_START_RELATIVE

XSD label Dataelement_12_4

Data model label RADIATION_THERAPY_START_RELATIVE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Date of start of radiation therapy

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

NATURAL_NUMBER [week] ($0 \leq x$)

XSD parent form Form5 - form_29_ver-5

XSD description

Start of the radiation therapy in weeks since initial diagnosis. For combined therapies, they should be entered as separate therapies.

Data model description

Start of the radiation therapy in weeks since initial diagnosis. For combined therapies, they should be entered as separate therapies.

4.4 Dataelement_13_2 - RADIATION_THERAPY_END_RELATIVE

XSD label Dataelement_13_2

Data model label RADIATION_THERAPY_END_RELATIVE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Date of end of radiation therapy

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

NATURAL_NUMBER [week] ($0 \leq x$)

XSD parent form Form5 - form_29_ver-5

XSD description

End of the radiation therapy in weeks since initial diagnosis.

Data model description

End of the radiation therapy in weeks since initial diagnosis.

4.5 Dataelement_14_3 - MM_MICROSAT_INSTABILITY

XSD label Dataelement_14_3

Data model label MM_MICROSAT_INSTABILITY

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Microsatellite instability

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

”YES”

”NO”

”NOT_DONE”

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [no; yes; not done]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Microsatellites analysed BAT26, D17S250, D5S346, BAT40, D2S123 and BAT25. Image cytometry does not qualify for comparability reasons

Data model description

Microsatellites analysed BAT26, D17S250, D5S346, BAT40, D2S123 and BAT25. Image cytometry does not qualify for comparability reasons

4.6 Dataelement_15_2 - MM_MISMATCH_REPAIR_GE

XSD label Dataelement_15_2

Data model label MM_MISMATCH_REPAIR_GE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Mismatch repair gene expression

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

”LOSS_OF_EXPRESSION”

”EXPRESSION”

”NOT_DONE”

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [expression; loss of expression; not done]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Mismatch repair gene expression – IHC array for different genes (common for 3). Expression of MLH1, MSH2, PMS2 and MSH6

Data model description

Mismatch repair gene expression – IHC array for different genes (common for 3). Expression of MLH1, MSH2, PMS2 and MSH6

4.7 Dataelement_16_3 - MM_RISK_SITUATION_HNPCC

XSD label Dataelement_16_3

Data model label MM_RISK_SITUATION_HNPCC

Level in data model OPTIONAL

XSD name Risk situation (only HNPCC)

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

YES_NO [] ((true|false|yes|no|f|t))

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Risk situation (only HNPCC), Amsterdam criteria

Data model description

Risk situation (only HNPCC), Amsterdam criteria

4.8 Dataelement_20_3 - MM_KRAS_MUTATION_KRAS_EX2

XSD label Dataelement_20_3

Data model label MM_KRAS_MUTATION_KRAS_EX2

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name KRAS exon 2 (codons 12 or 13)

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Not mutated"

"Mutated"

"Not done"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Mutated; Not mutated; Not done]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

KRAS exon 2 (codons 12 or 13) mutation status

Data model description

KRAS exon 2 (codons 12 or 13) mutation status

4.9 Dataelement_21_5 - MM_KRAS_MUTATION_KRAS_EX3

XSD label Dataelement_21_5

Data model label MM_KRAS_MUTATION_KRAS_EX3

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name KRAS exon 3 (codons 59 or 61)

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Not mutated"

"Mutated"

"Not done"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Mutated; Not mutated; Not done]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

KRAS exon 3 (codons 59 or 61) mutation status

Data model description

KRAS exon 3 (codons 59 or 61) mutation status

4.10 Dataelement_22_4 - MM_KRAS_MUTATION_KRAS_EX4

XSD label Dataelement_22_4

Data model label MM_KRAS_MUTATION_KRAS_EX4

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name KRAS exon 4 (codons 117 or 146) mutation status

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

”Not mutated”

”Mutated”

”Not done”

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Mutated; Not mutated; Not done]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

KRAS exon 4 (codons 117 or 146)

Data model description

KRAS exon 4 (codons 117 or 146)

4.11 Dataelement_23_5 - MM_KRAS_MUTATION_NRAS_EX2

XSD label Dataelement_23_5

Data model label MM_KRAS_MUTATION_NRAS_EX2

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name NRAS exon 2 (codons 12 or 13)

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Not mutated"

"Mutated"

"Not done"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Mutated; Not mutated; Not done]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

NRAS exon 2 (codons 12 or 13) mutation status

Data model description

NRAS exon 2 (codons 12 or 13) mutation status

4.12 Dataelement_24_4 - MM_KRAS_MUTATION_NRAS_EX3

XSD label Dataelement_24_4

Data model label MM_KRAS_MUTATION_NRAS_EX3

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name NRAS exon 3 (codons 59 or 61)

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Not mutated"

"Mutated"

"Not done"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Mutated; Not mutated; Not done]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

NRAS exon 3 (codons 59 or 61) mutation status

Data model description

NRAS exon 3 (codons 59 or 61) mutation status

4.13 Dataelement_25_3 - MM_KRAS_MUTATION_NRAS_EX4

XSD label Dataelement_25_3

Data model label MM_KRAS_MUTATION_NRAS_EX4

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name NRAS exon 4 (codons 117 or 146)

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Not mutated"

"Mutated"

"Not done"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Mutated; Not mutated; Not done]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

NRAS exon 4 (codons 117 or 146) mutation status

Data model description

NRAS exon 4 (codons 117 or 146) mutation status

4.14 Dataelement_2_2 - CLINICAL_STUDY_PARTICIPANT

XSD label Dataelement_2_2

Data model label CLINICAL_STUDY_PARTICIPANT

Level in data model OPTIONAL

XSD name Participation in clinical study

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

YES_NO [] ((true|false|yes|no|f|t))

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Participation in clinical study

Data model description

Participation in clinical study

4.15 Dataelement_30_3 - DIAG_MRI_DONE

XSD label Dataelement_30_3

Data model label DIAG_MRI_DONE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name MRI

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"MRI - Unknown"
"MRI - Done, data not available"
"MRI - Done, data available"
"MRI - Not done"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Done, data available; Done, data not available; Not
↪ done; Unknown]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

MRI diagnostic exam. This value shall be TRUE only if they were done within the context of the primary diagnosis. The values are advertising what is available in the biobank after further request and data is not provided as a part of collecting the central data set.

Data model description

MRI diagnostic exam. This value shall be TRUE only if they were done within the context of the primary diagnosis. The values are advertising what is available in the biobank after further request and data is not provided as a part of collecting the central data set.

4.16 Dataelement_31_3 - DIAG_CT_DONE

XSD label Dataelement_31_3

Data model label DIAG_CT_DONE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name CT

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"CT - Unknown"

"CT - Done, data not available"

"CT - Done, data available"

"CT- Not done"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Done, data available; Done, data not available; Not
↪ done; Unknown]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Diagnostic exam CT. This value shall be TRUE only if they were done within the context of the primary diagnosis. The values are advertising what is available in the biobank after further request and data is not provided as a part of collecting the central data set.

Data model description

Diagnostic exam CT. This value shall be TRUE only if they were done within the context of the primary diagnosis. The values are advertising what is available in the biobank after further request and data is not provided as a part of collecting the central data set.

4.17 Dataelement_33_1 - THERAPY_RESPONSE

XSD label Dataelement_33_1

Data model label THERAPY_RESPONSE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Specific response

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Specific response - Complete response"

"Specific response - Partial response"

"Specific response - Stable disease"

"Specific response - Progressive disease"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Complete response; Partial response; Progressive
↪ disease; Stable disease]

XSD parent form Form4 - form_31_ver-2

XSD description

Response to therapy - Specific response

Data model description

Response to therapy - Specific response

4.18 Dataelement_34_1 - THERAPY_RESPONSE_TIMESTAMP_RELATIVE

XSD label Dataelement_34_1

Data model label THERAPY_RESPONSE_TIMESTAMP_RELATIVE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Date response was obtained in weeks since initial diagnosis

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

NATURAL_NUMBER [] ($0 \leq x$)

XSD parent form Form4 - form_31_ver-2

XSD description

Date response was obtained in weeks since initial diagnosis

Data model description

Date response was obtained in weeks since initial diagnosis

4.19 Dataelement_35_3 - TARGETED_THERAPY_START_RELATIVE

XSD label Dataelement_35_3

Data model label TARGETED_THERAPY_START_RELATIVE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Date of start of targeted therapy

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

NATURAL_NUMBER [] ($0 \leq x$)

XSD parent form Form6 - form_30_ver-3

XSD description

Targeted therapy - Date of start (weeks since initial diagnosis)

Data model description

Targeted therapy - Date of start (weeks since initial diagnosis)

4.20 Dataelement_36_1 - TARGETED_THERAPY_END_RELATIVE

XSD label Dataelement_36_1

Data model label TARGETED_THERAPY_END_RELATIVE

Level in data model OPTIONAL

XSD name Date of end of targeted therapy

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

NATURAL_NUMBER [] ($0 \leq x$)

XSD parent form Form6 - form_30_ver-3

XSD description

Targeted therapy - Date of end (weeks since initial diagnosis)

Data model description

Targeted therapy - Date of end (weeks since initial diagnosis)

4.21 Dataelement_3_1 - AGE_AT_PRIMARY_DIAGNOSIS

XSD label Dataelement_3_1

Data model label AGE_AT_PRIMARY_DIAGNOSIS

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Age at diagnosis (rounded to years)

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

NATURAL_NUMBER [a] ($0 \leq x$)

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Age at initial histopathological diagnosis (biopsy or surgical specimen of the primary tumor) rounded to years.

Data model description

Age at initial histopathological diagnosis (biopsy or surgical specimen of the primary tumor) rounded to years.

4.22 Dataelement_49_1 - SURGERY_TYPE

XSD label Dataelement_49_1

Data model label SURGERY_TYPE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Surgery type

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Other"
"Endo-rectal tumor resection"
"Abdomino-perineal resection"
"Anterior resection of rectum"
"Low anteroir colon resection"
"Pan-procto colectomy"
"Total colectomy"
"Sigmoid colectomy"
"Transverse colectomy"
"Left hemicolectomy"
"Right hemicolectomy"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Abdomino-perineal resection; Anterior resection of
↪ rectum; Endo-rectal tumor resection; Left hemicolectomy; Low
↪ anteroir colon resection; Pan-procto colectomy; Right
↪ hemicolectomy; Sigmoid colectomy; Total colectomy; Transverse
↪ colectomy; Other]

XSD parent form Form - form_32_ver-8

XSD description

Surgery type

Data model description

Surgery type

4.23 Dataelement_4_3 - TIME_OF_RECURRENCE_RELATIVE

XSD label Dataelement_4_3

Data model label TIME_OF_RECURRENCE_RELATIVE

Level in data model OPTIONAL

XSD name Time of recurrence (metastasis diagnosis)

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

NATURAL_NUMBER [week] ($0 \leq x$)

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Weeks between primary diagnosis and diagnosed recurrence. If only months is available, conversion is weeks := months * 4. Any re-occurrence of cancer, be it a local re-occurrence, a lymph node metastasis, or a distant metastasis

Data model description

Weeks between primary diagnosis and diagnosed recurrence. If only months is available, conversion is weeks := months * 4. Any re-occurrence of cancer, be it a local re-occurrence, a lymph node metastasis, or a distant metastasis

4.24 Dataelement_51_3 - DATE_DIAGNOSIS

XSD label Dataelement_51_3

Data model label DATE_DIAGNOSIS

Level in data model OPTIONAL

XSD name Date of diagnosis

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

DATE [] (ISO_8601_WITH_DAYS)

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Date at which colon cancer was diagnosed for the first time. Histopathological diagnosis by biopsy or surgery qualifies as primary diagnosis

Data model description

Date at which colon cancer was diagnosed for the first time. Histopathological diagnosis by biopsy or surgery qualifies as primary diagnosis

4.25 Dataelement_53_3 - WHO_GRADE_VERSION

XSD label Dataelement_53_3

Data model label WHO_GRADE_VERSION

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name WHO version

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Not known"

"1st edition"

"2nd edition"

"3rd edition"

"4th edition"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [1st ed. (1979-1990); 2nd ed. (1991-2000); 3rd ed.
↪ (2001-2010); 4th ed. (used since 2011); Edition not known]

XSD parent form Form2 - form_34_ver-22

XSD description

The version of the WHO classification system used. Version years: 4th ed. (used since 2011), 3rd ed. (2001-2010), 2nd ed. (1991-2000), 1st ed. (1979-1990)

Data model description

The version of the WHO classification system used

4.26 Dataelement_54_2 - SAMPLE_MATERIAL_TYPE

XSD label Dataelement_54_2

Data model label SAMPLE_MATERIAL_TYPE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Material type

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Other"

"Healthy colon tissue"

"Tumor"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Healthy colon tissue; Tumor tissue; Other]

XSD parent form Form1 - form_35_ver-6

XSD description

Type of specimen

Data model description

Type of specimen

4.27 Dataelement_55_2 - SAMPLE_PRESERVATION_MODE

XSD label Dataelement_55_2

Data model label SAMPLE_PRESERVATION_MODE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Preservation mode

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Other"

"Cryopreservation"

"FFPE"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Cryopreservation; FFPE; Other]

XSD parent form Form1 - form_35_ver-6

XSD description

The preservation mode for the specimen

Data model description

The preservation mode for the specimen

4.28 Dataelement_56_2 - SAMPLE_ID

XSD label Dataelement_56_2

Data model label SAMPLE_ID

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Sample ID

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

TEXT [] ()

XSD parent form Form1 - form_35_ver-6

XSD description

An identifier, unique within the biobank

Data model description

An identifier, unique within the biobank

4.29 Dataelement_57_3 - DIGITAL_IMAGING_AVAILABILITY

XSD label Dataelement_57_3

Data model label DIGITAL_IMAGING_AVAILABILITY

Level in data model OPTIONAL

XSD name Availability digital imaging

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

”No”

”Can be generated”

”Readily available”

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Can be generated; No; Readily available]

XSD parent form Form2 - form_34_ver-22

XSD description

Do you have high-resolution digital imaging (corresponding to magnification 40x) from the histopathology?. Only scans of the surgical material should be considered here. The rationale is that smaller sections of the material (e.g., biopsies) do not contain sufficiently representative material for machine learning approaches

Data model description

Do you have high-resolution digital imaging (corresponding to magnification 40x) from the histopathology?. Only scans of the surgical material should be considered here. The rationale is that smaller sections of the material (e.g., biopsies) do not contain sufficiently representative material for machine learning approaches. Resolutions should be <0.125um/pixel (this is more accurate description of 40x).

4.30 Dataelement_58_2 - DIGITAL_IMAGING_INVASION_FRONT_AVAILABILITY

XSD label Dataelement_58_2

Data model label DIGITAL_IMAGING_INVASION_FRONT_AVAILABILITY

Level in data model OPTIONAL

XSD name Availability invasion front digital imaging

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Invasion front not included"

"Readily available"

"Can be generated"

"No"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Can be generated; Invasion front not included; No;
↪ Readily available]

XSD parent form Form2 - form_34_ver-22

XSD description

Do you have high-resolution digital imaging (corresponding to magnification 40x) containing invasion front from the histopatology?

Data model description

Do you have high-resolution digital imaging (corresponding to magnification 40x) containing invasion front from the histopatology?

4.31 Dataelement_59_5 - PHARMACOTHERAPY_SCHEME

XSD label Dataelement_59_5

Data model label PHARMACOTHERAPY_SCHEME

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Scheme of pharmacotherapy

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Other"

"Scheme of pharmacotherapy - 5-FU 325-350 mg/m² + LV 20 mg/m²i.v.

↳ bolus, day1-5, weeks 1 and 5"

"Scheme of pharmacotherapy - 5-FU 400 mg/m² + 100 mg i.v. bolus, d

↳ 1,2, 11,12,21,22"

"Scheme of pharmacotherapy - 5-FU 225 mg/m² i.v. continuous infusion,

↳ 5 days per week"

"Scheme of pharmacotherapy - 5-FU 1000 mg/m² i.v. continuous infusion,

↳ day 1-5, weeks 1 and 5"

"Scheme of pharmacotherapy - Capecitabine 800-825 mg/m² bid po, day 1

↳ -5, together with radiation or continuously untill end of

↳ radiation"

"Scheme of pharmacotherapy - UFT (300-340mg/m²/day) and LV (22.5-90 mg

↳ /day) po continuously, 5(-7) days per week, together with

↳ radiotherapy"

"Scheme of pharmacotherapy - Only preoperatively (no standard): 5-FU

↳ 250 mg/m² i.v. continuous infusion on days 1-13 nad 22-35 and

↳ oxaliplatin 50mg/m² i.v. day 1,8,22 and 29"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [5-FU 1000 mg/m² i.v. continuous infusion, day 1-5,

↳ weeks 1 and 5; 5-FU 225 mg/m² i.v. continuous infusion, 5 days

↳ per week; 5-FU 325-350 mg/m² + LV 20 mg/m²i.v. bolus, day1-5,

↳ weeks 1 and 5; 5-FU 400 mg/m² + 100 mg i.v. bolus, d 1,2,

↳ 11,12,21,22; Capecitabine 800-825 mg/m² bid po, day 1-5,

↳ together with radiation or continuously untill end of radiation;

↳ Only preoperatively (no standard): 5-FU 250 mg/m² i.v.

↳ continuous infusion on days 1-13 nad 22-35 and oxaliplatin 50mg/

- ↪ m2 i.v. day 1,8,22 and 29; UFT (300-340mg/m2/day) and LV (22.5
- ↪ -90 mg/day) po continuously, 5(-7) days per week, together with
- ↪ radiotherapy; Other]

XSD parent form Form3 - form_33_ver-10

XSD description

Scheme of pharmacotherapy. If the therapy was terminated or changed (e.g., dosage reduced), "Other" shall be selected. Additional textual information should be provided in such a case, see PHARMACOTHERAPY_SCHEME_DESCRIPTION

Data model description

Scheme of pharmacotherapy. If the therapy was terminated or changed (e.g., dosage reduced), "Other" shall be selected. Additional textual information should be provided in such a case, see PHARMACOTHERAPY_SCHEME_DESCRIPTION

4.32 Dataelement_5_2 - VITAL_STATUS

XSD label Dataelement_5_2

Data model label VITAL_STATUS

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Vital status

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"ALIVE"

"DEATH_COLON_CANCER"

"DEATH_OTHER"

"DEATH_UNKNOWN_REASON"

"UNKNOWN"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [death due to colon cancer; death due to other reasons;
↪ death for unknown reasons; person is still alive; unknown]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Vital status

Data model description

Vital status

4.33 Dataelement_61_5 - DIAG_LIVER_IMAGING_DONE

XSD label Dataelement_61_5

Data model label DIAG_LIVER_IMAGING_DONE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Liver imaging

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Liver imaging - Unknown Not done"

"Liver imaging - Done, data available"

"Liver imaging - Done, data not available"

"Liver imaging - Unknown"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Done, data available; Done, data not available; Not
↪ done; Unknown]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Liver imaging diagnostic exam. This value shall be TRUE only if they were done within the context of the primary diagnosis. The values are advertising what is available in the biobank after further request and data is not provided as a part of collecting the central data set.

Data model description

Liver imaging diagnostic exam. This value shall be TRUE only if they were done within the context of the primary diagnosis. The values are advertising what is available in the biobank after further request and data is not provided as a part of collecting the central data set.

4.34 Dataelement_63_4 - DIAG_X_DONE

XSD label Dataelement_63_4

Data model label DIAG_X_DONE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Lung imaging

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Lung imaging - Not done"
"Lung imaging - Done, data available"
"Lung imaging - Done, data not available"
"Lung imaging - Unknown"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Done, data available; Done, data not available; Not
↪ done; Unknown]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Lung imaging diagnostic exam. If CT or MRI or PET scan is available, this should be also considered one of the "Done" options. This value shall be TRUE only if they were done within the context of the primary diagnosis. The values are advertising what is available in the biobank after further request and data is not provided as a part of collecting the central data set.

Data model description

Lung imaging diagnostic exam. If CT or MRI or PET scan is available, this should be also considered one of the "Done" options. This value shall be TRUE only if they were done within the context of the primary diagnosis. The values are advertising what is available in the biobank after further request and data is not provided as a part of collecting the central data set.

4.35 Dataelement_67_1 - SURGERY_TYPE_OTHER

XSD label Dataelement_67_1

Data model label SURGERY_TYPE_OTHER

Level in data model OPTIONAL

XSD name Other surgery type

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

TEXT [] ()

XSD parent form Form - form_32_ver-8

XSD description

Surgery type, if not present on the list

Data model description

Surgery type, if not present on the list

4.36 Dataelement_68_2 - HIST_METASTASIS

XSD label Dataelement_68_2

Data model label HIST_METASTASIS

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Localization of metastasis

XSD type Not defined.

List of permitted values in XSD

"Localization of metastasis - None"
"Localization of metastasis - Pulmonary"
"Localization of metastasis - Osseous"
"Localization of metastasis - Hepatic"
"Localization of metastasis - Brain"
"Localization of metastasis - Lymph nodes"
"Localization of metastasis - Bone marrow"
"Localization of metastasis - Pleura"
"Localization of metastasis - Peritoneum"
"Localization of metastasis - Adrenals"
"Localization of metastasis - Skin"
"Localization of metastasis - Others"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Adrenals; Bone marrow; Brain; Hepatic; Lymph nodes;
↪ None; Osseous; Peritoneum; Pleura; Pulmonary; Skin; Others]

XSD parent form Form2 - form_34_ver-22

XSD description

Histopathology part - Localization of metastasis

Data model description

Histopathology part - Localization of metastasis. Multiple metastases can be added, each with its own location. This is intended for primary diagnosis only.

4.37 Dataelement_6_3 - VITAL_STATUS_TIMESTAMP

XSD label Dataelement_6_3

Data model label VITAL_STATUS_TIMESTAMP

Level in data model if(VITAL_STATUS!=UNKNOWN){REQUIRED}else{OPTIONAL}

XSD name Timestamp of last update of vital status

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

DATE [] (ISO_8601_WITH_DAYS)

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Timestamp of last update of vital status

Data model description

Timestamp of last update of vital status

4.38 Dataelement_70_2 - UICC_STAGE

XSD label Dataelement_70_2

Data model label UICC_STAGE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Stage

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Stage - IV"

"Stage - III"

"Stage - II"

"Stage - IVC"

"Stage - IIC"

"Stage - IVB"

"Stage - IVA"

"Stage - IIIC"

"Stage - IIIB"

"Stage - IIIA"

"Stage - IIB"

"Stage - II A"

"Stage - I"

"Stage - 0"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [0; I; II; II A; IIB; IIC; III; IIIA; IIIB; IIIC; IV;
↪ IVA; IVB; IVC]

XSD parent form Form2 - form_34_ver-22

XSD description

UICC Stage. The stages list is based on 8th edition, and backwards compatible with earlier editions.

Data model description

UICC Stage. The stages list is based on 8th edition, and backwards compatible with earlier editions.

4.39 Dataelement_71_1 - TNM_PRIMARY_TUMOR

XSD label Dataelement_71_1

Data model label TNM_PRIMARY_TUMOR

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Primary Tumor

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Primary Tumor - T4"

"Primary Tumor - T4b"

"Primary Tumor - T4a"

"Primary Tumor - T3"

"Primary Tumor - T2"

"Primary Tumor - T1"

"Primary Tumor - Tis"

"Primary Tumor - T0"

"Primary Tumor - TX"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [T0; T1; T2; T3; T4; T4a; T4b; Tis; TX]

XSD parent form Form2 - form_34_ver-22

XSD description

TNM Primary Tumor. It shall be interpreted as pTN - for tumor samples and biopsies, as the TN should come from the sample or biopsy. M may come from imaging (hence it may come from cTNM clinical assessment). Rationale: pTNM - is more reliable and should be available for tumors and biopsies

Data model description

TNM Primary Tumor. It shall be interpreted as pTN - for tumor samples and biopsies, as the TN should come from the sample or biopsy. M may come from imaging (hence it may come from cTNM clinical assessment). Rationale: pTNM - is more reliable and should be available for tumors and biopsies

4.40 Dataelement_73_3 - UICC_VERSION

XSD label Dataelement_73_3

Data model label UICC_VERSION

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name UICC version

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"8th edition"

"Not known"

"7th edition"

"6th edition"

"5th edition"

"4th edition or earlier"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [4th. ed (used before 1998); 5th. ed (used 1998-2002);
↪ 6th. ed (used 2003-2009); 7th ed. (used 2010-2017); 8th ed. (
↪ used since 2017); Not known]

XSD parent form Form2 - form_34_ver-22

XSD description

The version of the UICC system under which the staging was done. Version years:8th edition (since 2017),7th edition (used 2010-2017),6th. ed (used 2003-2009),5th. ed (used 1998-2002),4th. ed (used before 1998)

Data model description

The version of the UICC system under which the staging was done

4.41 Dataelement_75_1 - TNM_DISTANT_METASTASIS

XSD label Dataelement_75_1

Data model label TNM_DISTANT_METASTASIS

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Distant metastasis

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Distant metastasis - MX"
"Distant metastasis - M1c"
"Distant metastasis - M0"
"Distant metastasis - M1"
"Distant metastasis - M1a"
"Distant metastasis - M1b"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [M0; M1; M1a; M1b; M1c; MX]

XSD parent form Form2 - form_34_ver-22

XSD description

TNM - Distant metastasis. It shall be interpreted as pTN - for tumor samples and biopsies, as the TN should come from the sample or biopsy. M may come from imaging (hence it may come from cTNM clinical assessment). Rationale: pTNM - is more reliable and should be available for tumors and biopsies

Data model description

TNM - Distant metastasis. It shall be interpreted as pTN - for tumor samples and biopsies, as the TN should come from the sample or biopsy. M may come from imaging (hence it may come from cTNM clinical assessment). Rationale: pTNM - is more reliable and should be available for tumors and biopsies

4.42 Dataelement_77_1 - TNM_REGIONAL_LYMPH_NODES

XSD label Dataelement_77_1

Data model label TNM_REGIONAL_LYMPH_NODES

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Regional lymph nodes

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Regional lymph nodes - N3"
"Regional lymph nodes - NX"
"Regional lymph nodes - N0"
"Regional lymph nodes - N1"
"Regional lymph nodes - N1a"
"Regional lymph nodes - N1b"
"Regional lymph nodes - N1c"
"Regional lymph nodes - N2"
"Regional lymph nodes - N2a"
"Regional lymph nodes - N2b"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [N0; N1; N1a; N1b; N1c; N2; N2a; N2b; N3; NX]

XSD parent form Form2 - form_34_ver-22

XSD description

TNM - Regional lymph nodes. It shall be interpreted as pTN - for tumor samples and biopsies, as the TN should come from the sample or biopsy. M may come from imaging (hence it may come from cTNM clinical assessment). Rationale: pTNM - is more reliable and should be available for tumors and biopsies

Data model description

TNM - Regional lymph nodes. It shall be interpreted as pTN - for tumor samples and biopsies, as the TN should come from the sample or biopsy. M may come from imaging (hence it may come from cTNM clinical assessment). Rationale: pTNM - is more reliable and should be available for tumors and biopsies

4.43 Dataelement_7_2 - OVERALL_SURVIVAL_STATUS

XSD label Dataelement_7_2

Data model label OVERALL_SURVIVAL_STATUS

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Overall survival status

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

NATURAL_NUMBER [week] ($0 \leq x$)

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Weeks after first colon cancer therapy started for the given person. If the data is collected at the source in months only, the conversion should be weeks := months*4

Data model description

Weeks after first colon cancer therapy started for the given person. If the data is collected at the source in months only, the conversion should be weeks := months*4

4.44 Dataelement_81_3 - PHARMACOTHERAPY_SCHEME_DESCRIPTION

XSD label Dataelement_81_3

Data model label PHARMACOTHERAPY_SCHEME_DESCRIPTION

Level in data model if(PHARMACOTHERAPY_SCHEME==Other){REQUIRED}else{OPTIONAL}

XSD name Other pharmacotherapy scheme

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

TEXT [] ()

XSD parent form Form3 - form_33_ver-10

XSD description

Other pharmacotherapy scheme. When Other option is selected for pharmacotherapy scheme, the plain text description shall be provided. The plain text must include at least the chemical compounds used, the dosage and timing is optional

Data model description

Other pharmacotherapy scheme. When Other option is selected for pharmacotherapy scheme, the plain text description shall be provided. The plain text must include at least the chemical compounds used, the dosage and timing is optional

4.45 Dataelement_82_1 - BIOLOGICAL_MATERIAL_FROM_RECURRENCE_AVAILABLE

XSD label Dataelement_82_1

Data model label BIOLOGICAL_MATERIAL_FROM_RECURRENCE_AVAILABLE

Level in data model OPTIONAL

XSD name Biological material from recurrence available

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

YES_NO [] ((true|false|yes|no|f|t))

XSD parent form Form2 - form_34_ver-22

XSD description

Biological material from recurrence available

Data model description

Biological material from recurrence available

4.46 Dataelement_83_1 - WHO_GRADE

XSD label Dataelement_83_1

Data model label WHO_GRADE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Grade

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"WHO Grading - Grade - G1"

"WHO Grading - Grade - G2"

"WHO Grading - Grade - G3"

"WHO Grading - Grade - G4"

"WHO Grading - Grade - GX"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [G1; G2; G3; G4; GX]

XSD parent form Form2 - form_34_ver-22

XSD description

Grade. For Sweden "medium high" shall map to G3, and "low medium" shall map to G2. This has to be documented in the provenance information

Data model description

Grade. For Sweden "medium high" shall map to G3, and "low medium" shall map to G2. This has to be documented in the provenance information

4.47 Dataelement_85_1 - SEX

XSD label Dataelement_85_1

Data model label SEX

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Biological sex

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"other"

"female"

"male"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [female; male; other]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Biological sex of the person, defined by chromosomes.

Data model description

Biological sex of the person, defined by chromosomes.

4.48 Dataelement_87_1 - BRAF_PIC3CA_HER_MUTATION_STATUS

XSD label Dataelement_87_1

Data model label BRAF_PIC3CA_HER_MUTATION_STATUS

Level in data model OPTIONAL

XSD name BRAF, PIC3CA, HER2 mutation status

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"BRAF, PIC3CA, HER2 mutation status - Partial information available"

"BRAF, PIC3CA, HER2 mutation status - not mutated"

"BRAF, PIC3CA, HER2 mutation status - mutated"

"BRAF, PIC3CA, HER2 mutation status - not done"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Mutated; Not mutated; Partial information available;
↪ Not done]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

BRAF, PIC3CA, HER2 mutation status. If only 1 or 2 of the three mutation analyses have been done, the "Partial information available" value shall be selected

Data model description

BRAF, PIC3CA, HER2 mutation status. If only 1 or 2 of the three mutation analyses have been done, the "Partial information available" value shall be selected

4.49 Dataelement_88_1 - DIAG_COLONOSCOPY

XSD label Dataelement_88_1

Data model label DIAG_COLONOSCOPY

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Colonoscopy

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Colonoscopy diagnostic exam- Unknown"

"Colonoscopy diagnostic exam- Not done"

"Colonoscopy diagnostic exam - Negative"

"Colonoscopy diagnostic exam - Positive"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Negative; Positive; Not done; Unknown]

XSD parent form Form - form_28_ver-27

XSD description

Colonoscopy - Diagnostic exam. In case of rectal cancer, use rectoscopy also qualifies to answer TRUE here. But only rectoscopy in case of colon cancer does NOT qualify for TRUE. If the colonoscopy has been done outside of the biobank or the result is not available for some reason, the answer can be "not done". This value shall be TRUE only if they were done within the context of the primary diagnosis. The values are advertising what is available in the biobank after further request and data is not provided as a part of collecting the central data set.

Data model description

Colonoscopy - Diagnostic exam. In case of rectal cancer, use rectoscopy also qualifies to answer TRUE here. But only rectoscopy in case of colon cancer does NOT qualify for TRUE. If the colonoscopy has been done outside of the biobank or the result is not available for some reason, the answer can be "not done". This value shall be TRUE only if they were done within the context of the primary diagnosis. The values are advertising what is available in the biobank after further request and data is not provided as a part of collecting the central data set.

4.50 Dataelement_89_3 - YEAR_OF_SAMPLE_COLLECTION

XSD label Dataelement_89_3

Data model label YEAR_OF_SAMPLE_COLLECTION

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Year of sample collection

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

NATURAL_NUMBER [years] ($0 \leq x$)

XSD parent form Form1 - form_35_ver-6

XSD description

Calendar year in which the sample was collected.(YYYY)

Data model description

Calender year in which the sample was collected.

4.51 Dataelement_8_3 - SURGERY_START_RELATIVE

XSD label Dataelement_8_3

Data model label SURGERY_START_RELATIVE

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Time difference between initial diagnosis and surgery

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD Not defined.

Type in data model

NATURAL_NUMBER [week] ($0 \leq x$)

XSD parent form Form - form_32_ver-8

XSD description

Time difference between initial diagnosis and surgery. Weeks between initial diagnosis and date of surgery. Pre-operatively treated cases (neoadjuvant therapy) are welcome, but there needs to be surgery later on anyway, to have also sufficient amount of biological material.

Data model description

Time difference between initial diagnosis and surgery. Weeks between initial diagnosis and date of surgery. Pre-operatively treated cases (neoadjuvant therapy) are welcome, but there needs to be surgery later on anyway, to have also sufficient amount of biological material.

4.52 Dataelement_91_1 - HIST_MORPHOLOGY

XSD label Dataelement_91_1

Data model label HIST_MORPHOLOGY

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Morphology

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Signet ring cell carcinoma"
"Cribriform comedo-type adenocarcinoma"
"Adenocarcinoma"
"Mucinous carcinoma"
"Signet-ring cell carcinoma"
"Medullary carcinoma"
"High-grade neuroendocrine carcinoma"
"Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma"
"small cell neuroendocrine carcinoma"
"Squamous cell carcinoma"
"Adeonsquamous carcinoma"
"Micropapillary carcinoma"
"Serrated adenocarcinoma"
"Spindle cell carcinoma"
"Mixed adenoneuroendocrine carcinoma"
"Undifferentiated carcinoma"
"Other"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [Adenocarcinoma; Adeonsquamous carcinoma; High-grade
↪ neuroendocrine carcinoma; Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma;
↪ Medullary carcinoma; Micropapillary carcinoma; Mixed
↪ adenoneuroendocrine carcinoma; Mucinous carcinoma; Serrated
↪ adenocarcinoma; Signet-ring cell carcinoma; small cell
↪ neuroendocrine carcinoma; Spindle cell carcinoma; Squamous cell
↪ carcinoma; Undifferentiated carcinoma; Other]

XSD parent form Form2 - form_34_ver-22

XSD description

Histopathology Part - Morphology. This is a mandatory part of histopathological diagnosis, therefore it should be available. If really not available, "Other" may be used, but it is a sign of insufficient data detail

Data model description

Histopathology Part - Morphology. This is a mandatory part of histopathological diagnosis, therefore it should be available. If really not available, "Other" may be used, but it is a sign of insufficient data detail

4.53 Dataelement_92_1 - HIST_LOCALIZATION

XSD label Dataelement_92_1

Data model label HIST_LOCALIZATION

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Localization of primary tumor

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Localization of primary tumor - C20"
"Localization of primary tumor - C19"
"Localization of primary tumor - C18.7"
"Localization of primary tumor - C18.6"
"Localization of primary tumor - C18.5"
"Localization of primary tumor - C18.4"
"Localization of primary tumor - C18.3"
"Localization of primary tumor - C18.2"
"Localization of primary tumor - C18.1"
"Localization of primary tumor - C18.0"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [C 18.0 - Caecum; C 18.1 - Appendix; C 18.2 - Ascending
↪ colon; C 18.3 - Hepatic flexure; C 18.4 - Transverse colon; C
↪ 18.5 - Splenic flexure; C 18.6 - Descending colon; C 18.7 -
↪ Sigmoid colon; C 19 - Rectosigmoid junction; C 20 - Rectum]

XSD parent form Form2 - form_34_ver-22

XSD description

Histopathology part - Localization of primary tumor

Data model description

Histopathology part - Localization of primary tumor

4.54 Dataelement_93_1 - SURGERY_LOCATION

XSD label Dataelement_93_1

Data model label SURGERY_LOCATION

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Location of the tumor

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"Location of tumor - C18.0"
"Location of tumor - C18.1"
"Location of tumor - C18.2"
"Location of tumor - C18.3"
"Location of tumor - C18.4"
"Location of tumor - C18.5"
"Location of tumor - C18.6"
"Location of tumor - C18.7"
"Location of tumor - C19"
"Location of tumor - C19.9"
"Location of tumor - C20"
"Location of tumor - C20.9"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [C 18.0 - Cecum; C 18.1 - Appendix; C 18.2 - Ascending
↪ (right); C 18.3 - Hepatic flexure; C 18.4 - Transverse colon; C
↪ 18.5 - Splenic flexure; C 18.6 - Descending (left); C 18.7 -
↪ Sigmoid; C 19 - Rectosigmoid; C 19.9 - Rectosigmoid; C 20 -
↪ Rectum; C 20.9 - Rectum]

XSD parent form Form - form_32_ver-8

XSD description

Location of the tumor

Data model description

Location of the tumor

4.55 Dataelement_9_2 - SURGERY_RADICALITY

XSD label Dataelement_9_2

Data model label SURGERY_RADICALITY

Level in data model REQUIRED

XSD name Surgery radicality

XSD type xs:string

List of permitted values in XSD

"R2"

"R1"

"R0"

"RX"

Type in data model

LIST_OF_VALUES [R0; R1; R2; RX]

XSD parent form Form - form_32_ver-8

XSD description

Whether the surgery removed the entire tumor.

Data model description

Whether the surgery removed the entire tumor.